

INFLUENCE OF ROUGHNESS ON INITIAL IN VITRO RESPONSES OF OSTEOBLASTS AND hADMSC CELLS TO AN ALUMINA TOUGHENED ZIRCONIA (ATZ) NANOCOMPOSITE

Catuxa Prado², Silvia Pérez¹, Marta Suárez², Adolfo Fernández², José S. Moya², Ramón Torrecillas², Luis A. Díaz²

¹Transplants, Cell Therapy and Regenerative Medicine Unit, Central University Hospital of Asturias (HUCA), Oviedo, Spain, silviapelo@gmail.com

²Centro de Investigación en Nanomateriales y Nanotecnología (CINN) Consejo Superior de Investigaciones Científicas (CSIC) - Universidad de Oviedo (UO) - Principado de Asturias (PA), Avda. de la Vega, 4-6, 33940- El Entrego, Asturias, Spain, la.diaz@cinn.es (corresponding autor)

Keywords: Al₂O₃/Ce-TZP nanocomposite, surface roughness, in vitro biological response.

ABSTRACT

Ceramic materials appear as a very interesting alternative to metals for dental applications especially thanks to their aesthetic advantages. Nevertheless, their inherent brittleness is a major drawback that limits their use in load bearing applications such as dental implants and abutments. The great increase in fracture toughness reached in alumina and ceria stabilized zirconia nanocomposites opens the possibility of using these nanostructured materials for dental components demanding high mechanical performance. Moreover, surface roughness can be adjusted by sandblasting with different materials. The purpose of the present study was to perform in vitro osteogenic differentiation assays growing a human osteoblast-like cell line, SaOs-2, and hADMSCs (human adipose mesenchymal stem cells) on different sandblasted ATZ supports in order to determine the influence of the material's nature on the behavior of the cells.

In vitro studies carried out to assess the biocompatibility of a ATZ nanocomposite demonstrated its non-citotoxicity and haemocompatibility. Furthermore, different osteogenic genes showing that the roughness and the nature of the material are favorable for cell osteogenic differentiation were studied.

In conclusion, the ceria-stabilized zirconia-alumina nanocomposite presented in this work exhibits a high potential for application in the fabrication of dental implants due to their biological behavior and very promising mechanical properties.

1 INTRODUCTION

During more than 40 years, commercially pure titanium and titanium alloys were widely used as dental implant materials due to their excellent biocompatibility, early osseointegration and high corrosion resistance [1]. Nevertheless, titanium may induce allergic reactions or sensitivities [2] and it possesses a dark color that could be exposed during peri-implant mucosa recession and ruin the entire aesthetic result [3]. Ceramics as a viable alternative to resolve these problems were developed. Bioceramic materials offer excellent opportunities to combine the absence of metal ions, good bone ingrowth characteristics and improved aesthetics due to the possibility of dyeing the product with pigments. In this context, Alumina (Al₂O₃) was the first bioceramic used as an implant material [4], due to its low friction, wettability, wear resistance and biocompatibility. However, it showed insufficient physical properties. In the 80s, Zirconia (ZrO₂) emerged as a ceramic material valid for implants because of its improved fracture toughness and mechanical strength with respect to alumina. Tetragonal zirconia polycrystals, specially 3 mol% yttria-stabilized zirconia (3Y-TZP), serves as a metal substitute in substrates and possesses good physical characteristics; its bending strength doubles and its fracture toughness almost triples that of alumina [5]. Nevertheless, the big disadvantage of pure 3Y-TZP is its low temperature degradation (LTD) [6]. Actually, combining the positive properties of Al₂O₃ (wear resistance, hydrothermal stability and hardness) with those of ZrO₂ (strength and fracture toughness) it is possible to obtain Alumina Toughened Zirconia (ATZ) and Zirconia Toughened Alumina (ZTA) nanocomposites with a higher potential for application in dental implants [7]. Among

them, composite materials of Ce-TZP and alumina have shown very promising mechanical properties to be used in the fabrication of implants [8]. Besides the mechanical properties of the bulk material, the characteristics of an implant's surface, such as composition, topography and roughness play an important role in cell-material integration [9] and biocompatibility. The interaction between cells and a biomaterial's surface is fundamentally relevant and essential in terms of the response of cells at the interface, affecting the growth and quality of newly formed bone tissue [10, 11]. For this reason cell culture models are routinely used to study the response of osteoblastic cells in contact with different substrates for implantation in bone tissue. Moreover, adipose-derived stromal cells (ADSCs) are considered to contain a group of pluripotent mesenchymal stem cells and manifest multilineage differentiation capacity, including osteogenesis, chondrogenesis and adipogenesis [12]. These last cells could differentiate into odontogenic lineage, expressing bone marker proteins, and might be used as suitable seeding cells for tooth regeneration [13]. Few data are available concerning the response of mesenchymal stem cells to ATZ. The purpose of the present study was to perform *in vitro* osteogenic differentiation assays growing a human osteoblast-like cell line, SaOs-2, and hADMSCs (human adipose mesenchymal stem cells) on different ATZ supports in order to determine the influence of the material's nature on the behavior of the cells in relation with these new implants. In this context, different tests were performed to study cytotoxicity, viability, haemolysis and differences in terms of osteogenic and apoptotic gene expression between the samples (ALPL, alkaline phosphatase; BGLAP, bone gamma-carboxyglutamate protein; COL1A1, collagen type I, alpha 1 chain; IBSP, integrin bone sialoprotein; SPARC, secreted protein acidic and cysteine rich; and the gene CASPASE 3 as an indicator of apoptotic damage).

2 EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

The Al₂O₃/Ce-TZP nanocomposite was made using the following materials: Ce-TZP (10mol% CeO₂) from Daichi (Japan) with an average particle size of 35 nm (D₅₀) and a specific surface area of 15 m².gr⁻¹, α-Al₂O₃ powder (TM DAR, Taimei Chemical Co.- Japan) with a specific surface area of 14,6 m².gr⁻¹ and an average particle size of 150 nm. In addition, the following chemical precursors were also used: i) aluminum chloride (Sigma-Aldrich, Spain), ii) zirconium IV-propoxide (70% solution in 1-propanol) (Sigma-Aldrich, Spain), iii) 99,9% 2-Propanol from Panreac (Spain) and iv) 99.97% absolute ethanol (Panreac, Spain). The colloidal processing route to obtain this nanocomposite is described in Rivera et al. [1].

2.1 Disk specimen preparation

The powders were cold isostatically pressed at 300 MPa into cylindrical rods of 50 mm in length and 9 mm in diameter. After surface machining and firing at 1475°C for one hour, disk-shaped specimens of 7 mm diameter and 1.3 mm thickness were prepared by cutting and polishing (applying microcrystalline diamonds of 9, 3 and 1 microns). In total, 36 disks were used for sandblasting tests and six more as target specimens.

2.2 Sandblasting process

Disks with white corundum and SiC powders were sandblasted (Table 1). Laser diffraction (Beckman Coulter LS 13 320, USA) was used for the granulometric characterization of the selected fractions. The air pressure was applied perpendicular to the surface of the disk at 0.4 bars and at a distance of 10 mm (Sandblaster I, Astursinter, Spain).

Samples	Sandblasting material
Sample NA	Non sandblasted sample (control)
Sample A	Sandblasted by: White Corundum < 90 μm, 60 s
Sample B	Sandblasted by: 90 μm < SiC < 250 μm, 15 s
Sample C	Sandblasted by: SiC < 90 μm, 15 s

Table 1: Sample references and materials used for surface treatment.

2.3 Surface roughness and morphology

The morphology of the samples and the raw materials used in the process of sandblasting was characterized by Field Emission Scanning Electron Microscopy (FESEM) (FEI: Quanta FEG 650, USA). The surface roughness of the specimens was analyzed using a surface roughness tester (MicroTest: MT4002, Spain). Six measurements on each specimen according to ISO 4287-1997 were performed. The assessed profile (Ra) as an arithmetical mean deviation was calculated. The amount of transformation (monoclinic volume content) induced by sandblasting was determined by X-ray diffraction (XRD) (Bruker Germany, D8) using the method of Toraya et al. [2]. The presence of alumina strongly enhanced the resistance of zirconia to low temperature degradation (LTD). This behavior was studied with a Tuttnauer Autoclave (2540EL) following ISO 13356:2008.

2.4 In vitro studies methodology

To assess the biocompatibility of the Al₂O₃/Ce-TZP nanocomposite demonstrated its non-cytotoxicity and haemocompatibility and different tests were carried out:

- 1) Human Adipose-derived Mesenchymal Stem Cells (hADMSCs) isolation and culture. hADMSCs were isolated from abdominal subcutaneous adipose tissue biopsies obtained from obese subjects undergoing gastric bypass surgery. Briefly, adipose tissue was washed in sterile PBS (Biowest, France) containing 1% penicillin and streptomycin (Lonza, Belgium); submitted to mechanical digestion and then digested with 0.02% Collagenase I (Sigma-Aldrich, USA) DMEM solution (Lonza, Belgium) after shaking for 2 hours at 37°C. The cell suspension was filtered with a 40 µm cell strainer (Corning, USA) and centrifuged at 300g for 10 minutes. The obtained cell fraction was plated in cell culture flasks and cultured in expansion medium: high-glucose DMEM media (Lonza, Belgium) supplemented with 10% FBS (Gibco, ThermoFisher scientific, USA) and 1% P/S (Lonza, Belgium) at 5% CO₂ and 37°C. Cells were cultured to 80% confluence and harvested using Trypsin-EDTA 1X (Biowest, France).
- 2) Citotoxicity tests using the Neutral Red Uptake (NRU) assay and the MTS assay. The potential cytotoxic effect of materials on mammalian cells was determined by using the Neutral Red Uptake (NRU) assay and the MTS assay. In the NRU test, the uptake of NR into the lysosomes/endosomes and vacuoles of living cells is used as a quantitative indication of viability. The MTS cytotoxicity assay is a colorimetric method that measures the reduction of the yellow MTS compound by mitochondrial reductases. Because the cellular reduction is only catalyzed by metabolically active cells, it is possible to quantify the percentage of living cells. The procedure followed was based on the direct contact method described in ISO 10993-part 5 [14] for biomaterials and medical device testing. Samples were sterilized by immersion in 70% ethanol overnight and rinsed twice in PBS before use. SaOs-2 cells (human osteosarcoma cells, kindly provided by the SCT of the University of Oviedo) or human MSCs from adipose tissue were seeded onto 48-well plates at a density of approximately 4·10⁴ cells/ml/cm² and cultured for 24 h for the formation of monolayers. After achieving confluence, the culture medium was replaced and samples were gently placed in contact with the cell monolayer. Wells seeded with the same amount cells were used as controls (blanks). In the NRU method, cells were washed after 24 h and incubated with neutral red solution (Neutral red solution 0.1 %, Scharlab, Spain) for 3 h. After that, cells were washed again and NR was desorbed by adding a mixture of ethanol and acetic acid. The amount of NR extracted from the cells was measured at 540 nm. The percentage of viable cells in each culture condition was calculated as:

$$\% \text{ of viable cells} = 100 \times \frac{\text{Abs}_{540}(\text{extract})}{\text{Abs}_{540}(\text{blank})}$$

In the MTS assay, culture medium was removed after 24 h and 1 ml of fresh medium with MTS solution (CellTiter 96® Aqueous One Solution Cell Proliferation Assay, Promega, USA) (5:1) was added to each well. MTS solution was prepared at 42mg/ml in PBS and 1ml

of PMS (Phenazine methosulfate; Sigma Aldrich, Germany) at 0.92mg/ml was mixed with 20 ml of MTS solution prior to use. After 3-4 additional hours in the presence of MTS, absorbance was determined at 490nm. All assays were conducted in triplicate. The percentage viability was calculated as:

$$\% \text{ of viable cells} = 100 \times \frac{\text{Abs}_{490}(\text{extract})}{\text{Abs}_{490}(\text{blank})}$$

- 3) The haemolysis index was determined following the norm ASTM F 756-08. Briefly, a quantitative colorimetric determination of haemoglobin (Hb) in human pooled whole blood anti-coagulated with Li-heparin from 3 donors (total blood hemoglobin - TBH) was made by mixing the blood with Drabkin's reagent. Hb released into plasma when blood was exposed to the materials was also measured. Samples were incubated for 3 h at 37 °C and inverted every 15 min. Then, samples were removed and tubes were centrifuged at 800 rpm (15 min). 100 µL of each supernatant were placed into a 96-well plate and Drabkin's reagent (100µL) was added. The cyanmethemoglobin produced by the reaction of Hb with the Drabkin's reagent was detected by spectrophotometry at 540 nm. The quantitative determination for Hb was made by creating a standard curve by two fold serial dilution of Hb (from 1.20 mg/ml to 0.01 mg/mL). poly-L-Lysine (Sigma-Aldrich, Germany) at a concentration of 1% (10 mg/mL) in sterile distilled water was used as the positive control (PC). Polyethylene glycol (Sigma Aldrich, Germany) at 40% in water was used as the negative control (NC). The hemolytic index was calculated as follows:

$$\text{Hemolytic Index} = \frac{\text{Hb released} \left(\frac{\text{mg}}{\text{mL}} \right)}{\text{TBH} \left(\frac{\text{mg}}{\text{mL}} \right)}$$

- 4) Osteogenic differentiation of SaOs-2 (human osteoblast-like cell line) and hADMSCs. Cells were seeded in a 48-well plate at a density of 50×10^3 cells on each of the four kinds of samples described. Once the cells were seeded on the samples they were differentiated. For osteogenic differentiation, MSCs or SaOs-2 were cultured in expansion medium supplemented with 0.1 µM dexamethasone, 50 µM ascorbic acid and 10mM β-glycerol phosphate (all reagents from Sigma-Aldrich, USA). Differentiation medium was changed every 72 hours, and the whole differentiation process was completed in 3 weeks. In order to confirm the adequate osteogenic differentiation, Alkaline phosphatase and Alizarin red staining were performed.
- 5) Alkaline phosphatase staining. Differentiated cells were washed twice with PBS and fixed with 4% formaldehyde (Merck, Germany) for 15 minutes. After this time, they were washed again with PBS and stained with a BCIP/NBT solution (SIGMA FAST™ BCIP/NBT, Sigma-Aldrich, USA) for 45 minutes at room temperature, according to the manufacturer's instructions. Under an inverted microscope, this staining was then visualized.
- 6) Alizarin red staining. Differentiated bone cells were washed twice with PBS and fixed with 10% paraformaldehyde for 45 minutes at 4°C. After this period, cells were washed twice with distilled water and stained with 2% alizarin red solution (Merck, Germany) for 5 minutes at room temperature. Finally, cells were washed, staining and observed by microscopy.
- 7) RNA extraction and cDNA synthesis. Total RNA was isolated using Tri reagent® solution (Ambion, USA) according to the manufacturer's instructions. The quality of the RNA was assessed through absorbance measurements made using a NanoDrop ND-1000 UV-Vis Spectrophotometer (NanoDropTechnologies, Wilmington, DE). All the samples used in the PCR procedures showed a 260/280 nm absorbance ratio between 1.8 and 2.2. A ratio of approximately 2 is accepted as pure for RNA. Each RNA sample was reverse transcribed using the iScript cDNA Synthesis Kit (Bio-Rad, Hercules, CA) following the manufacturer's instructions. The cDNA samples, stored at -20°C until use, were cooled at 4°C.
- 8) Real-Time quantitative polymerase chain reaction. The primers for the Caspase-3 and β-actin genes examined were designed by Beacon Designer software (Premier Biosoft International, CA) while other genes were designed for Sigma Aldrich KiCqStart™ SYBR® Green

Primers (Sigma Aldrich, USA). Quantitative PCR was performed using a CFX96 Real-Time System (Bio-Rad, Hercules, CA, USA). SYBR Green PCR Supermix (2X) (Bio-Rad), which detects amplification using Sybr Green as a double-stranded DNA specific fluorescent dye, was used as the mastermix. Assays in duplicate and a blank was included in every assay were performed. The reaction mixture for amplification comprised 2 μ L of cDNA, 0.4 μ L of each primer (forward and reverse primers; final concentration 0.1 μ M), 10 μ L of Sybr Green mix and sterile water in a final volume of 20 μ L. For the Sparc gene, the reaction mixture for amplification comprised 2 μ L of cDNA, 1.8 μ L of each primer (forward and reverse primers; final concentration 450 nM), 10 μ L of Sybr Green mix and sterile water in a final volume of 20 μ L. The RT-PCR protocol, in the case of Caspase-3 and β -Actin, included an initial step of 95°C (5 min), followed by 45 cycles of 15 sec at 94°C for DNA denaturation, 30 sec for primer annealing at 60°C and 1 minute at 55,7°C for primer extension. The primer extension step was performed at 59°C for the Alpl gene, at 60°C for the Sparc gene and, finally, at 63.3°C for the β -Glap, Ibsp and Col1 genes. Fluorescence data during the primer extension step were acquired. The melting-curve analysis, to confirm product specificity, was performed immediately after amplification, following 1 min of denaturation at 95°C, 1 min of annealing at 65°C and 60 cycles of 0.5°C increments (30 sec each) beginning at 65°C while monitoring fluorescence. Product identity was confirmed by electrophoresis with ethidium bromide-stained 2% agarose gel in 1X TBE buffer. β -Actin was used as the endogenous control. Table 2 provides the primer sequences as well as the RT-PCR parameters for the seven genes examined: bone differentiation genes ALPL, BGLAP, COL1, IBSP and SPARC and CASPASE 3 as an indicator of apoptotic damage. β -ACTIN was used as a normalized gene. CASPASE 3 and β -ACTIN primer sequences were designed using Beacon Designer software. The other primer sequences were designed for Sigma Aldrich.

Gene	Annealing temperature(°C)	Melting temperature(°C)	Sequence (5'-3')	Amplicon Size (bp)
ALPL	59 °C	85.5°C	F-AGT R-CGTCCCCG	
β ACTIN	57.0 °C	88.5°C	F- ACTACCTCATGAAGATCCTC R- CGGATGTCCACGTCACACTTC	
BGLAP	63.3 °C	83.5°C	F-TTCTTTCTCTTCCCCTTG R-CCTCTTCTGGAGTTTATTTGG	97
CASPASE-3	57 °C	83°C	F-CTGGACTGTGGCATTGAGAC R- ACAAAGCGACTGGATGAACC	159
COL1	63.3 °C	89.5°C	F-GCTATGATGAGAAATCAACCG R-TCATCTCCATTCTTTCCAGG	199
IBSP	63.3 °C	77°C	F-GGAGACTTCAAATGAAGGAG R-CAGAAAGTGTGGTATTCTCAG	80
SPARC	60 °C	80°C	F-AGTATGTGTAACAGGAGGAC R-AATGTTGCTAGTGTGATTGG	143

Table 2: Genes, annealing and melting temperatures, primer sequences and amplicon sizes of human genes tested by RT-PCR.

- 9) Statistical analysis. Data were statistically analyzed using the Proc MIXED procedure of the SAS/STAT v8.2 software package (SAS Institute, Inc., Cary, NC). Ct values (number of cycles needed to generate a fluorescent signal above a predefined threshold) and ΔCt values (difference between the Ct of the target gene and that of the housekeeping gene) for each gene and repetition were used as dependent variables. To quantify gene expression levels a relative standard method was used. The model fitted included the type of sample as the fixed effect and the sample as a random effect to account for the non-independency of the repetitions. For each sample level, least-square means and their corresponding standard errors were computed. For descriptive purposes, a Student's *t* test on raw Ct means computed for samples using Proc GLM of SAS/STAT was also carried out, assuming that the sample type effect included two independent groups of normally distributed observations.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The ATZ nanocomposite is composed of a matrix of Ce-TZP grains, size 400-500nm, and a homogeneously distributed second phase of alumina crystals, of an average size of 250nm. FESEM image of the microstructure of the ATZ nanocomposite is shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Polished surface of the ATZ nanocomposite by FESEM (secondary electrons). Ce-TZP crystals (grey color) constitute matrix and the darkness crystals are alumina.

The images after sandblasting with white corundum and silicon carbide for 90 s and 15 s are shown in Figure 3. Sandblasting with SiC <250 μm and >90 μm (Fig.3B) produces visibly larger voids and grooves than treating with white corundum and SiC with particles <90 microns (Fig3 A and C).

Figure 3: FESEM images from the topographical appearance of sandblasted surfaces with white corundum and silicon carbide raw materials. A) White corundum < 90 mm time: 60 s; B) SiC < 250 mm and > 90 mm time: 15 s; and C) SiC < 90 mm time 15 s.

In Table 3, the surface roughness values (R_a) of the ATZ specimens are summarized. According to the Altbretsson and Wennerberg classification [16], the samples sandblasted with white corundum present a “smooth” surface roughness ($R_a < 0,5 \mu\text{m}$), while the samples sandblasted with SiC show “minimally rough” and “moderately rough” surface roughnesses.

Raw materials	Ra < 0.5 μm	0.5 μm < Ra < 1.0 μm	1.0 μm < Ra < 2.0 μm	Ra > 2.0 μm
	Smooth*	Minimally rough*	Moderately rough*	Rough*
W.C.< 90 μm	0.465 \pm 0.06			
SiC 250-90 μm			1.358 \pm 0.11	
SiC < 90 μm		0.580 \pm 0.08		
N. S	0.031 \pm 0.10			

Table 3: Roughness values of the ATZ nanocomposite surfaces after sandblasting with corundum and SiC for 90 and 15 seconds (mean \pm SD in μm).N.S (No Sandblasting).

The volumetric fraction of the monoclinic phase was measured on as-sintered surfaces, as-sintered surfaces after sandblasting, as-sintered surfaces after 5h of ageing, polished surfaces and polished surfaces after a thermal treatment at 1200°C for 15 minutes with and without ageing for 5h and 24h. The volumetric fraction of the monoclinic phase was measured from XRD patterns using the expression proposed by Toraya et al. [17]. In Table 4, the volumetric fractions of monoclinic phase zirconia (V_m) present on the different sandblasted surfaces are shown. As can be seen, the materials do not present spontaneous phase transformation on their surface after sintering. Moreover, it can be appreciated that these materials do not undergo any hydrothermal ageing, not even after being subjected to very long and severe ageing treatments. However, sandblasting processes do lead to the transformation, under tension, of part of the tetragonal zirconia to monoclinic zirconia. This transformation process is reversible; in every case, a posterior thermal treatment at 1200°C for 15 minutes succeeds in transforming the totality of the monoclinic zirconia back to its initial tetragonal state. Furthermore, the surfaces subjected to this reversible process maintain their resistance to thermal ageing.

	Monoclinic phase content (V_m total)
ATZ as-sintered	3,80% \pm 3%
ATZ as-sintered and ageing during 5h	2,10% \pm 3%
ATZ as-sintered sandblasting surface by white corundum < 90 μm , 60 s	24,73% \pm 3%
ATZ as-sintered sandblasting surface by white corundum < 90 μm 60 s ageing during 5h	27,00% \pm 3%
ATZ as-sintered sandblasting surface by SiC 250-90 μm , 15 s.	48,70% \pm 3%
ATZ as-sintered sandblasting surface by SiC 250-90 μm , 15 s ageing during 5h	50,00% \pm 3%
ATZ as-sintered sandblasting surface by SiC <90 μm , 15s	31,70% \pm 3%
ATZ as-sintered sandblasting surface by SiC <90 μm , 15 s ageing during 5h	36,00% \pm 3%

Table 4: Volumetric fractions of monoclinic phase zirconia present on different sandblasted surfaces.

3.1. - Viability tests

The biocompatibility of the materials and the modified surfaces were evaluated in vitro following the ISO 10993 part 5 [14] (contact method). This standard procedure specifies that a material is considered non-cytotoxic when cell viability is above 70%. The potential cytotoxicity on SaOs-2 and MSCs was assessed by the MTS assay and the NRU method. MTS tests evaluate mitochondrial activity whereas NRU tests measure the incorporation of vital dye NR into the lysosomes/endosomes and vacuoles of living cells. Both the NRU and the MTS assays gave similar results, showing that none of the surface modification treatments induced significant cell death (Figure 4). Tissue culture polystyrene (TCPS) was used as the blank.

Figure 4: Biological assessment: NRU and MTS assays. No reduction in cell viability was observed for either the SaOs-2 (A) or the hADMSC (B) cells for any of the surface modifications tested, since the percentage viability was always superior to 70 %. Bars represent the means (SD) of triplicate measurements.

3.2. - Haemolysis test

Haemolysis is the alteration, dissolution or destruction of red blood cells that results in haemoglobin liberation into the surrounding medium. In the haemolysis assay, pooled human blood and test materials are co-incubated at 37°C and, following a centrifugation step to pellet intact red blood cells, the amount of hemoglobin released into the medium (as a measure of red blood cell disruption) is spectrophotometrically measured after reaction with Drabking's reagent. According to Stanley's classification criteria, a material is considered non-haemolytic for haemolytic indexes <2 while it is considered slightly haemolytic and haemolytic for haemolytic index values of 2-5 and >5, respectively. The studied ATZ nanocomposite can be considered non-haemolytic, since the haemolytic index is close to 0 (0.1-0.2) for all the surface modifications tested.

3.3. - Alkaline phosphatase and Alizarin red staining

Pictures showing alkaline phosphatase and Alizarin red staining (Figure 5 and 6 respectively) demonstrate the correct osteoblast differentiation of hADMSCs. All of the differentiated cells used for gene expression studies were stained and, consequently, osteoblast differentiation confirmed.

Figure 5: Alkaline phosphatase staining.

Figure 6: Alizarin red staining.

3.4. - qPCR

Product identity was confirmed by electrophoresis on ethidium bromide-stained 2% agarose gels in 1X TBE buffer, which resulted in a single product of the desired length. In addition, an iCycler iQ melting curve analysis was performed, which rendered single product specific melting temperatures. No primer-dimers were generated during the 40 real-time PCR cycles conducted. All polymerase chain reaction efficiencies were above 90% and linearity was high, with correlation coefficients (R^2) above 0.989.

3.5. - Gene expression

To quantify gene expression, the relative standard method (relative fold changes) was used and expression levels were determined for the ceramics and the control group (NA sample) by normalizing results with respect to β -ACTIN.

For hADMSCs, a discreet increase was noticed in the relative expression of four of the studied genes for samples A, B and C when compared with the control sample. In Figure 7, these increases are plotted. In the problem group, the genes BGLAP, CASPASE3, IBSP and SPARC were up-regulated 2.27-fold for sample A, 1.57-fold for sample C, 3.10-fold for sample A, and 2.27-fold for sample B, respectively, with respect to the basal levels recorded for the endogenous control (β -ACTIN). However, these increases were only significant ($p < 0.05$) in the case of IBSP for sample A.

Figure 7: Relative quantification of the studied genes. mRNA levels for apoptotic and bone differentiation genes recorded in hADMSCs (upper part) and SaOs-2 cells relative to endogenous control gene β -ACTIN levels. Values are expressed as mean \pm SEM. * indicates a significant difference with respect to the controls at p less than 0.05.

In the case of the SaOs cells, an even more discreet increase was observed in the relative expression of two of the studied genes for samples A, B and C when compared with the NA sample (control). These results are also shown in Figure 7. The IBSP gene is 1.55-fold up-regulated for sample B. The COL1A1 gene is up-regulated 2.95-fold for sample A, 2.85-fold for sample B and 1.74-fold for sample C with respect to the basal levels recorded for the endogenous control. In this case, differences between control and problem groups were not significant. In recent years, ceramics have become more promising as potential biomaterials for dental implant applications due to their biocompatibility properties. Despite their beneficial influence on bone response, their poor mechanical properties, which limit the scope of clinical application, are well-known ceramic material drawbacks. In the last years, ceramic nanocomposites have emerged as a very promising alternative to overcome the mechanical limitations of ceramics. 3Y-TZP ceramics are frequently used in dentistry and in association with alumina; zirconia is used in ceramic composites that are considered the bioinert ceramic reference for clinical applications. This biological inertness explains the good response in terms of biocompatibility and the absence of deleterious effects on cell viability. The biomaterial studied in this work is a Alumina Toughened Zirconia (ATZ) nanocomposite that combines the properties of Al_2O_3 , such as wear resistance, hydrothermal stability and hardness, with the strength and fracture toughness of Ce-ZrO₂. Moreover, Ce-TZP does not suffer low temperature degradation. The good combination of mechanical properties of this nanocomposite has already been proven and now it is necessary to confirm its good interaction with cells. The interaction between the biological medium and the material is critical to determine the success of an implant. The ideal material to make implants should not be purely tolerated by the host but should interact with biological systems in a way that induces the appropriate host response for a specific application [18]. The host response towards a biomaterial is dictated by the cells that respond to the biomaterial which, in turn, is controlled by the proteins that coat the surface of the biomaterial. Importantly, the nature and activity of the proteins adsorbed on the surface depend on the physical and chemical properties of the surface. Therefore, cell behavior depends indirectly on surface characteristics, which should be appropriate to actively promote an adequate and specific host response. For instance, for the efficacy of dental implants it is essential to establish intimate contact between the biomaterial's surface and bone structure elements; therefore, the biomaterial should permit cell adhesion, promote proliferation and avoid detrimental responses such as induction of cell death or inflammation. Cell attachment and adhesion phenomena belong to the first stages of material-cell interactions and will influence the capacity of cells to spread,

proliferate and differentiate. Importantly, adherent cells (like osteoblasts and fibroblasts) do not divide and even undergo apoptosis in case of adhesion deprivation [19]. Therefore, these early events strongly contribute to generate a successful host response and must be studied in research endeavors directed to develop new biomaterials for the design of bone contact implant devices. Biomaterial surface specifications can influence adsorption of biological molecules and, in the second stage, cell response. In fact, the biomaterial's surface properties, such as topography and hydrophilicity will be determinant in terms of biocompatibility and other biological phenomena. Over the years, in order to improve their wear properties, corrosion resistance and biocompatibility to biomaterials surface modifications have been applied. A series of studies has indicated that roughness stimulates the adhesion, growth and osteogenic differentiation of MSCs. In the literature, surfaces with $Ra \leq 1 \mu\text{m}$ are considered smooth and those with $Ra > 1 \mu\text{m}$ are described as rough. In general, the surface roughness range that favours osseous differentiation has been reported to be 1.0-1.5 μm [20]. In the present study, SaOs-2 cells and hADMSC cells were used to investigate the influence of roughness on regulation of cell viability, hemolysis and osseous differentiation. According to the results obtained in the cytotoxicity and hemolysis experiments, the data obtained in our study revealed that there are no significant differences in the responses of osteogenic cells and hADMSCs towards the different surface modification treatments in terms of biocompatibility. In fact, none of the surface modification treatments induced significant cell death in osteoblasts, hADMSC or erythrocytes. Similar results regarding cell viability and hemolysis have been published over the years [20, 21, 22]. Given the bioinertness of ceramic materials, such as those studied in this work, treatments to modify the surface and provide a suitable environment are necessary in order to trigger a favorable biological response in terms of osseous differentiation. Concerning gene expression, different osteogenic genes were studied in order to determine differences between samples. For hADMSCs the increase was only lightly observed in the case of four genes BGLAP, CASPASE3, IBSP and SPARC. BGLAP was up-regulated 2.27-fold for sample A, CASPASE3 was up-regulated 1.57-fold for sample C, IBSP was up-regulated 3.10-fold for sample A and, finally, SPARC was up-regulated 2.27-fold for sample B with respect to the basal levels. However, the increase was only significant ($p < 0.05$) in the case of IBSP in sample A. These findings in terms of gene expression as well as histological results showed that the roughness and the nature of the material are adequate to allow cells to achieve osteogenic differentiation, despite the fact that the surface roughness of the studied samples is clearly below the Ra values reported to favor osseous differentiation (1.0-1.5 μm). It is important to note that osteoblastic differentiation of MSCs into functional differentiated osteoblasts requires a series of steps involving the expression of different proteins at each stage. Alkaline phosphatase is regarded as a marker of early osteoblastic differentiation. In fact, it is the main signal that compromises cells to differentiate towards osteoblastic lineage; in a similar way, COL1 gene is over-expressed in the pre-osteoblastic phase coinciding with the beginning of the bone tissue-differentiating cascade, whereas secretion of Osteocalcin and IBSP as well as matrix mineralization is associated with the final differentiation phase. The observation of an increasing expression of IBSP with significant differences between groups for white corundum (sample A) showed that the differences in terms of osteogenic differentiation seem not to appear until the last phases, meaning that the gene expression pattern is similar for all samples during the entire process. Importantly, the main increase observed in IBSP is in agreement with the results obtained by Wang and cols. [23] that pointed out the importance of the integrin-linked kinase/ β -catenin pathway in mediating signals from topographic cues to direct the osteogenic differentiation of cells. For SaOs-2 cells, the three samples (A, B and C) showed upregulation related to sample NA (control) for two of the studied genes, IBSP and COL1. However, this upregulation was not significant in any case. The expected pattern for SaOs-2 cells is clearly different from that of hADMSC because it is a human osteoblast-like cell line itself and it is supposed to express osteogenic genes such as COL1 at the beginning of the bone tissue differentiating cascade or IBSP that are over expressed at middle-to-late osteogenic differentiation. These observations are in agreement with Czekanska et al. [24], who described high levels of expression of osteocalcin, bone sialoprotein, decorin and procollagen-I. For both types of cells (hADMSCs and SaOs), the apoptotic gene studied, Caspase-3, did not show important differences between samples, meaning that neither material nor roughness had a clear influence on cell death. This circumstance is in agreement with the absence of deleterious effects on cell viability.

4 CONCLUSIONS

The non-cytotoxicity and haemocompatibility of a nanocomposite ceramic material formed by alumina and ceria stabilized zirconia has been proved. The surface roughness of this nanocomposite can be adjusted depending on the particle size of the materials used for sandblasting. Smooth roughness values of around 0.5 μm are obtained when the abrasive material (white corundum or silicon carbide) is below 90 μm , while the use of silicon carbide particles of sizes between 90 and 250 μm leads to surface roughness values of around 1.5 μm . Moreover, the roughness and the nature of the material used have been proved adequate for cell osteogenic differentiation. An increase in the expression of BGLAP and IBSP genes was observed on samples sandblasted with white corundum below 90 μm , whereas SPARC gene was upregulated on samples sandblasted with SiC between 90 and 120 μm . Then, the studied nanocomposite is a very promising material for dental applications thanks to its good mechanical properties in comparison with conventional ceramics, the possibility of adjusting its surface roughness and the different in vitro results obtained.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The Spanish Ministry of Science, Innovation and Universities and the Spanish Higher Council for Scientific Research (CSIC) have supported this research under the Projects MAT2012-38645 and INPERIO, H2020-SMEInst-2018-2020-2 Ref CSIC-20185222 respectively. Catuxa Prado acknowledges financial support from the JAE-DOC program (CSIC).

REFERENCES

- [1] A.T.Sidambe. Biocompatibility of advanced manufactured titanium implants-A review. *Materials* 2014;7(12): 8168-8188.
- [2] A. Sicilia, S. Cuesta, G. Coma, I. Arregui, C. Guisasola, E. Ruiz, A. Maestro. Titanium allergy in dental implant patients: A clinical study on 1500 consecutive patients. *Clinical Oral Implants Research* 2008; 19(8): 823-835.
- [3] L. den Hartog, G.M. Raghoobar, JJH Slater, K. Stellingsma, A. Vissink, HJA Meijer. Single-tooth implants with different neck designs: A randomized clinical trial evaluating the aesthetic outcome. *Clinical Implant Dentistry and Related Research* 2013; 15(3): 311-321.
- [4] W Shulte, G. Heimke. The Tubinger immediate implant. *Quintessenz* 1976; 27: 17-23.
- [5] R.C. Garvie, R.H. Hannink, R.T.Pascoe. Ceramic steel?. *Nature* 1975; 258(5537): 703-704.
- [6] J. Chevalier, L. Gremillard L, Deville S. Low-temperature degradation of zirconia and implications for biomedical implants. *Annual Review of Materials Research* 2007; 37: 1-32.
- [7] J. Chevalier, L. Gremillard. Ceramics for medical applications: A picture for the next 20 years. *Journal of the European Ceramic Society* 2009; 29(7): 1245-1255.
- [8] S. Rivera, L.A. Díaz, A. Fernández, R. Torrecillas., J.S. Moya. Reinforcement mechanisms in alumina toughened zirconia nanocomposites with different stabilizing agents. 37th Int'l Conf & Expo on Advanced Ceramics & Composites (ICACC 2013). Daytona Congress, 2013.
- [9] A. Wennerberg, T. Albrektsson, B. Andersson. An animal study of c.p. titanium screws with different surface topographies. *J Mater Sci Mater Med* 1995; 6:302-309.
- [10] E. Lamers, X.F. Walboomers, M. Domanski, J. Riet, F.C.van Delft, R. Luttge, L.A. Winnubst, H.J. Gardeniers, J.A.Jansen. The influence of nanoscale grooved substrates on osteoblast behavior and extracellular matrix deposition. *Biomaterials* 2010; 31(12): 3307-16.

- [11] A. Pae, H. Lee, H.S. Kim, Y.D.Kwon, Y.H.Woo. Attachment and growth behaviour of human gingival fibroblasts on titanium and zirconia ceramic surfaces. *Biomedical Materials* 2009; 4(2): 025005.
- [12] Liu TM, Martina M, Hutmacher DW, Hui JH, Lee EH, Lim B. Identification of common pathways mediating differentiation of bone marrow and adipose tissue-derived human mesenchymal stem cells into three mesenchymal lineages. *Stem Cells* 2007; 25(3): 750-760.
- [13] Jing W, Wu L, Lin Y, Liu L, Tang W, Tian W. Odontogenic differentiation of adipose-derived stem cells for tooth regeneration: necessity, possibility, and strategy. *Med Hypotheses* 2008; 70(3): 540-542.
- [14] ISO 10993-5:2009 Biological evaluation of medical devices - Part 5: Tests for in vitro cytotoxicity
- [15] ASTM F756 – 08. Standard Practice for Assessment of Hemolytic Properties of Materials. American Society of Testing Materials. 2008.
- [16] Albrektsson T, Wennerberg A. Oral implant surfaces: part 1- review focusing on topographic and chemical properties of different surfaces and in vivo responses to them. *Int. J. Prosthodont* 2004; 17: 536-546.
- [17] Toraya H, Yoshimura M, Somiya M. Calibration curve for quantitative analysis of the monoclinic tetragonal ZrO₂ system by X-rays diffraction. *J. Am. Ceram. Soc* 1984; 67: 119-121.
- [18] Williams DF. Definitions in biomaterials: proceedings of a consensus conference of the European Society for Biomaterials, Chester, England, March 3-5, 1986. European Society for Biomaterials.
- [19] Straface E, Natalini B, Monti D, Franceschi C, Schettini G, Bisaglia M, Fumelli C, Pincelli C, Pellicciari R, Malorni W. C3-fullero-tris-methanodicarboxylic acid protects epithelial cells from radiation-induced anoikia by influencing cell adhesion ability. *FEBS Lett.* 1999; 454(3):335-40.
- [20] Hempel U, Hefti T, Kalbacova M, Wolf-Brandstetter C, Dieter P, Schlottig F. Response of osteoblast-like SAOS-2 cells to zirconia ceramics with different surface topographies. *Clinical Oral Implants Research.* 2010; 21: 174-181.
- [21] Gautam C, Joyner J, Gautam A, Rao J, Vajtai R. Zirconia based dental ceramics: structure, mechanical properties, biocompatibility and applications. *Dalton Trans.* 2016; 45:19194-19215.
- [22] Yamashita D, Machigashira M, Miyamoto M, Takeuchi H, Noguchi K, Izumi Y, Ban S. Effect of surface roughness on initial responses of osteoblast-like cells on two types of zirconia. *Dental Materials Journal.* 2009; 28: 461–470.
- [23] Wang W, Zhao L, Wu K, Ma Q, Mei S, Chu PK, Wang Q, Zhang Y. The role of integrin-linked kinase/ β -catenin pathway in the enhanced MG63 differentiation by micro/nano-textured topography. *Biomaterials* 2013; 34(3): 631-40.
- [24] Czekanska EM, Stoddart MJ, Richards RG, Hayes JS. In search of an osteoblast cell model for in vitro research. *Eur Cell Mater* 2012; 24: 1-17.